

A MULTISCALE STOCHASTIC APPROACH FOR THE STUDY OF THE NONLINEAR TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF PLANT FIBRE COMPOSITES

A. Del Mastro^{1*}, F. Trivaudey¹, V. Guicheret-Retel¹
V. Placet¹, L. Boubakar¹

¹ Département de Mécanique Appliquée, Institut Femto-ST
Univ. Bourgogne Franche-Comté
CNRS/UFC/ENSM/UTBM
24 rue de l'Épitaphe, 25000 Besançon, France
e-mail (*) : alessandra.del_mastro@univ-fcomte.fr

Keywords: Plant fibre composites, multiscale modelling, stochastic computation

ABSTRACT

In view of the global and major ecological challenge we are facing, the minimisation of the environmental impact of the structures and vehicles, both at the stages of their elaboration and of their exploitation, is a main issue. In this context, the use of biomass, in the form of fibres and/or building blocks, for the development of structural composites is a promising solution. However, plant fibres exhibit generally a relatively complex and non-linear tensile behaviour. The characterisation and understanding of the origin of this non-linearity, as well as its variability, represent an important challenge for the sustainable use of plant fibres as reinforcement of semi-structural composites. This work proposes to investigate the mechanisms that underlie such complex mechanical behaviour using a numerical approach based on a multiscale stochastic modelling. The unidirectional composite ply is modelled via a representative elementary volume (RVE). The RVE consists of a non-twisted yarn impregnated with epoxy matrix. A stochastic method is implemented and used to evaluate the influence of microstructural features on the tensile response of the ply. The microstructure of the RVE and the parameters of the behaviour's laws of its constituents are defined using random drawings within an experimental database. The tensile response of the generated RVE is simulated using finite elements analysis. This first study is focused on the geometrical parameters of the microstructure. The preliminary results show that for cylindrical fibres, their dimensions and the scattering in their dimension have no influence on the shape of the nonlinear tensile behaviour of the REV of the ply.

1 INTRODUCTION

Plant fibre composites have been booming in recent years in many industrial sectors. While short-fibre and non-woven solutions have reached a good level of technology readiness, continuous fibres reinforced composite solutions are still at an early stage of development.

Nevertheless, interesting results have been collected in recent years [1] demonstrating the potential PFCs (Plant Fibre Composites) use for semi-structural applications.

Several works [2-4] point out also a non-linear response at the scale of UD (unidirectional) composites which are tensile loaded. The origins of this behaviour remain open to discussion in the PFCs' community. Several years ago, several hypotheses were proposed. They attributed the origin of this non-linear response to mechanisms occurring at different scales (reorientation of cellulose microfibrils or fibres themselves within twisted yarns). Nowadays technological advances make non-twisted yarn possible to be manufactured, for certain plant fibres, such as flax. Thus, purely unidirectional tapes are now commercialised. In the UD composites made of such purely UD reinforcement, a nonlinear tensile response is still observed [5]. These results seem to support the hypothesis that the non-linear behaviour of PFCs results from the non-linear behaviour of the plant fibres themselves, at least partly. Indeed, a nonlinear behaviour is generally observed at the scale of elementary fibres [6], and sometimes also at the scale of technical fibres. Some previous works carried out in our team showed that this behaviour results from the ultrastructure of the fibre (initial MFA and its possible evolution under mechanical loading [7]), morphological considerations (degree of ellipticity in particular [8]) and also time-delayed

mechanisms.

This work proposes to investigate the mechanisms that underlie the non-linear behaviour of PFCs using a stochastic multi-scale approach. The mechanical behaviour is investigated using a representative elementary volume (REV) of the UD ply (Fig. 1). For this study, the morphological parameters and materials correspond to those of hemp fibres and epoxy matrix. Nevertheless, the tools and models developed and presented here are adaptable to all types of plant fibres and polymers.

The RVE consists of a non-twisted yarn impregnated with epoxy matrix. Indeed, experimental observations show that the geometry of the fibres is non-uniform and heterogeneous and their distribution within the matrix is not periodic. So, we propose here to consider the impregnated yarn as being the portion of material that can represent the overall behaviour of the ply. This unit cell seems to be the smallest periodic volume in the material (see Fig. 1).

The microscopic observation of the cross-section of UD PFC (see Fig.1) show that the yarn consists of individualized fibres and also small bundles (also sometimes called technical fibres) made of several elementary fibres. We consider in this work, as an initial approach, an ideal yarn which consists of perfectly individualized fibres only. Within the REV, the fibre wall is considered to be an anisotropic viscoelastic material of which behaviour model is derived from work previously developed in our team [7].

Concerning the stochastic aspects, this work focuses on the influence of the microstructural features and in particular of geometrical and dimensional features. Indeed, it is well known that the morphology of the plant fibres is very variable. Their distribution within the yarn section can also be random. So, the microstructure of the REV by drawing random variables out of the probability distribution laws of the fibre morphological parameters. These distribution laws were obtained from previous experiments. For each drawing and generated microstructure, the tensile response of the RVE of the UD ply is simulated by FEM.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the multiscale stochastic approach. The REV allows the influence of geometric and material uncertainties occurring at the nano and microscopic levels on the tensile behavior at higher scales (meso and macroscopic) to be evaluated.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1 REV definition

The implementation of a micromechanical approach requires defining a Representative Elementary Volume of the studied material. In the literature, several definitions of REV can be found [9].

Figure 2: Cross section of an UD fibre composite ply (a), impregnated yarn (b) and of the geometrical model of a randomly generated REV (c).

They are united in stating that the REV should contain enough information about the microstructure and at the same time be sufficiently small when compared to the structural dimensions at the macroscopic scale. To be correctly defined, the REV has to meet the two following conditions: (i) represent a unit cell in a periodic microstructure, and (ii) constitute a volume containing a very large number (mathematically infinite) of microscale elements, possessing statistically homogeneous and ergodic propertiesⁱ [10].

In the case of UD PFCs, experimental observation shows that the geometry of the fibres is non-uniform and heterogeneous and that their distribution in the matrix is not periodic. So, contrary to most of the approaches used for classical composites made of glass or carbon fibres, the unit cell in PFCs is not described by a single fibre embedded in matrix. In PFCs, a pseudo-periodicity exists between the microscopic scale (elementary fibres, bundles, porosities ...) and the mesoscopic one (ply) (Fig. 2). Thus, the yarn embedded in the matrix is considered as the periodic unit cell.

A simplified microstructure is chosen as a first step. The complex morphology of the fibres is simplified and the fibres are modelled as thick-walled cylindrical tubes. The REV is designed as a volume with a hexagonal transverse section containing a sufficient number of fibres. This one is representative of the number of fibres observed in an industrially produced yarn, which is about one hundred elementary fibres.

2.2 Stochastic approach

The stochastic part of this work is expressed in the form of a succession of deterministic FE simulations made at the scale of the randomly generated REV. The parameterization of each REV results from a random drawing of the variables out of their probability distribution. In this study, the main interest is focused on the fibre geometrical and dimensional parameters, and in particular on their internal and external dimensions.

The method described by the flowchart in Fig. 3 consists of an initialization step, three main steps and a post-processing step. A Matlab® script controls the various steps, as well as the exchanges between the different software used. All tasks, unless otherwise specified, are performed in the Matlab® environment as well.

Initialization

In this work, a number of input parameters have been set:

- Number of simulations demanded;

- Minimum fibre volume fraction;
- REV geometry (hexagonal section);
- Meshing parameters;
- Parameters of the behaviour's law of the constituents (fibres and resin).

The initialization step allows to set the values for these various parameters.

Figure 3: Flow-chart of the analysis phases (a) and details regarding the algorithm for fibre generation (b).

STEP 1: Generation of the REV's microstructure

This step consists essentially in generating the microstructure of the REV in the (x,y) plane. The idea is to generate the fibres and arrange them in the hexagonal cross-section area so as to complete the required fibre / matrix ratio. To do this, the algorithm whose flowchart is displayed in Fig. 3b is used. It also consists of three sub-steps:

- Generating the possible positions in the 2D space: This initial phase consists of creating a high number of points in the REV section. These points represent the possible positions of the centres of the fibres constituting the yarn in its cross-section area. The coordinates of these points are created randomly for each simulation carried out in order to keep the randomness of the spatial distribution of the fibres.
- Random drawing of the fibres, one by one: this step allows to define the morphological parameters (internal and external diameters) of the fibres making up the REV. For this study, the parameters that are considered as stochastic variables are the geometric parameters only. Each selection i corresponds to a generated fibre.

- Positioning of the fibres: this step of the algorithm allows to place the centre of the fibre generated in the previous step in the section of the REV avoiding the superposition of two or more fibres. The algorithm identifies the points among those generated previously which allows to position the i -th fibre without causing overlaps. The generated fibre is randomly centred on one of the identified possible positions. The fibre fraction is therefore updated. A test is performed at each iteration until the required fibre volume fraction is reached. Then, the algorithm continues to position the fibres until there are no more positions available to centre other fibres without overlapping. The geometry is thus validated.

STEP 2: Mesh

Once the microstructure in the cross-section of the REV is completely defined, the mesh step allows to discretize the geometry and to generate the nodes and the connectivities necessary for the finite elements analysis. The mesh is generated using the free software GMSH [11]. At the output of *STEP 1*, the 2D geometry of the created section is imported into GMSH which performs a surface meshing. This meshing is then extruded in the z direction in order to obtain the 3D geometry of the REV.

STEP 3: Simulation

Once the model is created, the tensile test on the REV is simulated using the FE commercial code Abaqus®. The global deformations reached during the simulations are low and the calculations are therefore carried out using an implicit scheme. The calculations are carried out using a quad-core dual processor with 36 GB of RAM.

Post-processing

After each simulation, a python script is executed for the automatic extraction of the results. Once the data is obtained, a Matlab® routine is dedicated to post-processing and storing data. The calculation time for each run and finite element simulation is 2 hours maximum.

2.3 FE model

Solid 8 noded elements are used to model the REV. The fibres are discretized using 20 elements on the outer and inner contours. The REV has 12 elements for each edge of the hexagon and 40 in the height. The conditions of periodicity are imposed by the application of the boundary conditions on the 6 lateral surfaces of the REV (Fig. 4) according to equation:

$$\forall P \in S_i, \quad \vec{u}(P) \cdot \vec{n}_i = 0 \quad i = [1,6] \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Boundary conditions applied to simulate the tensile test.

The simulations of the tensile tests are performed by imposing a nodal displacement at all nodes belonging to the upper surface of the volume. The amplitude of the displacement is chosen in order to impose a deformation rate comparable to that applied experimentally in the quasi-static test, i.e.

$\dot{\varepsilon} = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. The simulated maximum global deformation is equal to 2%. The bottom surface is embedded to prevent rigid body movements. The global stress is obtained as the ratio between the sum of the reactions to the imposed nodal displacements and the surface area of the REV. This surface is calculated by taking into account the porosities (lumens) and neglecting the variations which happen during the tensile test.

2.4 Behaviour law

Fibre wall

For this study, an anisotropic viscoelastic behaviour is implemented to model the fibres. The wall of the fibres is considered as a composite material in which the reinforcement and the matrix are respectively represented by the cellulose microfibrils and by a mixture of hemicellulose and lignin. The elastic properties are calculated by homogenization [12], the viscoelastic parameters were previously identified by inverse method using creep tests performed on elementary fibres [13, 14]. The model is described in details in Trivaudey et al. [7]. The parameters used, both elastic and viscoelastic, are summarized in Table 1. In this study, the reorientation of microfibrils in the fibre wall during the tensile test is taken into account, with an initial angle (MFA) equal to 11° for all the fibres.

Elastic properties		Viscoelastic parameters	
E_L	75 GPa	β_{LT}	12.25
E_T	11 GPa	β_T	1.5
ν_{LT}	0.153	zn_c	2.45
G_{LT}	2.52 GPa	zn_0	1.9
ν_{TT}	0.2		–

Table 1: Elastic and viscoelastic parameters used to feed the fibre behaviour model. Directions L and T correspond to the longitudinal and transverse directions in the local reference frame linked to the microfibrils [7].

Matrix and porosity

Concerning the matrix, in this work, its behaviour is considered purely elastic, with $E = 4$ GPa and $\nu = 0.34$. The damaged and plastic behaviour will be taken into account in a future work. The porosities taken into account in this work correspond to the total volume of voids (lumen) in the REV. These areas are considered to have zero rigidity. The porosities generated during the manufacturing process of the composite, within the matrix, are not taken into account in this first version of the work.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Characterization of the generated microstructures

A first sequence of 100 simulations is carried out to evaluate the impact of the fibre dimensional parameters on the behaviour of the REV of the UD ply. To do this, the diameters of the fibres and the lumens are drawn randomly out of the probability distributions of the fibre wall cross-sectional areas. The parameters of the probability laws, identified in a previous work from an experimental database, are summarized in Table 2.

Since the generation process of the REV microstructures is random, an analysis of the geometrical characteristics of the REVs obtained is carried out.

For each generated REV, the probability distributions of the surfaces of the fibres and the lumens are in agreement with those identified from the experimental observation. The differences between the values of the parameters identified from the experiments and the generated microstructures are shown in Table 2. Results show that the method proposed to generate the microstructures is therefore able to efficiently and automatically reproduce the unit cells. As described previously, the REV generation algorithm takes as input the morphological parameters of the fibres, the size of the elementary volume and a minimum

value of fibre volume fraction. The resulting fibre and porosity volume fractions are then an outcome of the random drawing, as the positions of the centres. The probability distributions of the fibre and porosity fractions obtained for the simulated REV are shown in Fig. 5. The fibre volume fraction varies between 38% and 55% for the considered simulations. The porosity fraction is comprised between 7% and 8.8%.

	Fibre surface [μm^2]	Lumen surface [μm^2]
<i>Distribution law</i>	<i>Lognormal</i>	<i>Lognormal</i>
μ	6.9365	4.3371
σ	0.4734	0.8304
Maximum gap between experimental and generated distributions		
<i>Err</i> (μ)	0.121%	0.332%
<i>Err</i> (σ)	0.072%	0.008%

Table 2: Values of the parameters of the probability distribution laws estimated from the measurements of the cross-sectional areas of hemp fibre wall and lumen. Difference between these values and the ones identified from the generated VER.

Figure 5: Probability distributions of the fibres (a) and the porosity fractions (b) obtained.

3.2 Tensile test simulation: comparison with the literature

Fig. 6 proposes a stress-strain curve obtained by numerical simulation of a tensile test on a REV containing one hundred of elementary fibres impregnated in epoxy resin. The generated microstructure leads to a fibre volume fraction of 38%. In this figure, some experimental curves extracted from the literature are also reported. They concern flax-epoxy [15] and jute-polyester composites [5], failing to present results for hemp-epoxy UD composites. This first result shows that the stress levels obtained with the REV model used here are comparable to those observed experimentally for similar materials.

The shape of the curve is also close to the one experimentally observed for these PFCs. Nevertheless, it is possible to note that the yield point observed experimentally around 0.2% deformation is not reproduced by numerical simulation. The origin of this non-linearity experimentally observed is probably due to physical mechanisms that are not taken into account in our model, such as dissipative phenomena (damage and / or plasticity) that can occur within this type of composite. These mechanisms will be considered in the next step of this work, and the influence of the parameters of the behaviour

laws of the constituents on the response of the ply will be also quantified.

Figure 6: Comparison of the tensile behavior of various UD plant fibre composites reported in the literature from tests and simulations carried out from the representative volume of a hemp-epoxy ply presented in this study.

3.3 Tensile test simulation: influence of the geometric features

The results of the simulations obtained for the 100 tested REV_i are presented in Fig. 7. When observing the obtained results, we note that all the microstructures studied express the same type of tensile behaviour and non-linearity.

Figure 7: REV global tensile behavior with microstructures with variable fibres sizes (a). Apparent tangent moduli curves (b).

The apparent tangent modulus decreases as the axial deformation increases. Differences are observed, particularly with regard to rigidities. These appear to be led by the volume fraction of fibres,

rather than the size or distribution of the fibers themselves. This interpretation seems to be consistent with the results shown in Fig. 8a and 8b, in which three different REV's having exactly the same fibre content are compared in terms of global tensile behaviour. Their geometric characteristics are summarized in Fig.8c and 8d, in which the distributions of fibre and lumen surfaces obtained for the three REV's are compared. Even for different geometric characteristics, the tensile behaviour (Fig. 8a) and the apparent tangent modulus curves (Fig. 8b) show the same shape, with a variability in terms of rigidity less than 5% during the tensile test simulation.

However, at this stage of the work it is still difficult to distinguish the effects of the fibre size (or fibre size distribution) from the effect of the fibre volume fraction, since the random draws lead not only to a modification of the size and distribution of the fibres in the REV, but also to the fibres volume fraction. By determining the volume fraction of each of the REV's tested, and as expected, it appears that the highest rigidities are obtained for the microstructures which lead to the highest fibre content.

Calculations are under way on microstructures with high variable fibre size and distributions but identical volume fraction. These results would consolidate the previous conclusion.

Figure 8: Comparison of tensile behaviour (a), apparent tangent modulus curves (b) and the generated probability distribution functions of fibres (c) and lumen (d) surfaces for three REV having the same fibre content (44 %).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a methodology for the analysis of the mechanical behaviour of plant fibre composites based on a multi-scale stochastic approach. The composite ply is represented by an elementary volume consisting of a yarn of hemp fibres embedded in an epoxy matrix. The microstructures of the REV are generated automatically using random draws within the distribution laws of the geometrical parameters of hemp fibres. The results obtained from a first series of simulations show that:

- The geometrical characteristics of the generated REV microstructures respect the distributions obtained from experimental observation;
- The shape of the non-linearity remains the same for all simulated REVs.
- The apparent stiffness of the ply seems independent on the size and distribution of the fibres within the REV, at least when the latter have a circular transverse section;

These are only preliminary results, and they do not allow to decouple the influence of the fibres volume fraction and that of the geometrical parameters of the microstructure. In the future works, the REV generation method will be exploited in order to carry out a sensitivity analysis on the geometrical and morphological parameters on the tensile behavior of the REVs.

In the next steps, REVs with constant volume fraction with different microstructures will be simulated. The idea will be to vary the fibre dimensions in the REV, as well as their morphology, to finally evaluate the propagation of the geometric effects observed for the elementary fibers [8] on the scale of the UD reinforcement.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Camille François, a PhD student in the Department of Applied Mechanics at Femto-St Institute for providing the experimental data.

REFERENCES

- [1] D.U. Shah, P.J. Schubel, P. Licence, and M.J. Clifford, Determining the Minimum, Critical and Maximum Fibre Content for Twisted Yarn Reinforced Plant Fibre Composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72** (15), 2012, pp. 1909–17, [doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.08.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.08.005).
- [2] G Lebrun, A Couture, and L Laperrière, Tensile and Impregnation Behavior of Unidirectional Hemp/paper/epoxy and Flax/paper/epoxy Composites, *Composite Structures* **103**, 2013, pp. 151–60, [doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.04.028](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.04.028).
- [3] D.U. Shah, P.J. Schubel, P. Licence, and M.J. Clifford, The Tensile Behavior of off-Axis Loaded Plant Fiber Composites: An Insight on the Nonlinear Stress-Strain Response, *Polymer Composites*, **33** (9), 2012, pp. 1494–1504, [doi:10.1002/pc.22279](https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.22279).
- [4] D.U. Shah, P.J. Schubel, P. Licence, and M.J. Clifford, Determining the Minimum, Critical and Maximum Fibre Content for Twisted Yarn Reinforced Plant Fibre Composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72** (15), 2012, pp. 1909–17, [doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.08.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.08.005).
- [5] M Khalfallah, B. Abbès, F. Abbès, Y.Q. Guo, V. Marcel, A. Duval, F. Vanfleteren, F. Rousseau, Innovative Flax Tapes Reinforced Acrodur Biocomposites: A New Alternative for Automotive Applications, *Materials & Design*, **64**, 2014, pp. 116–26, [doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2014.07.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2014.07.029).
- [6] V.Placet, O. Cisse, and L. Boubakar, Influence of Environmental Relative Humidity on the Tensile and Rotational Behaviour of Hemp Fibres, *Journal of Materials Science*, **47** (7), 2012, pp. 3435–46, [doi:10.1007/s10853-011-6191-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-011-6191-3).
- [7] F. Trivaudey, V. Placet, V. Guicheret-Retel, L. Boubakar, Nonlinear Tensile Behaviour of Elementary Hemp Fibres. Part II: Modelling Using an Anisotropic Viscoelastic Constitutive Law in a Material Rotating Frame, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **68**, 2015, pp. 346–55, [doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.10.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.10.020).

- [8] A. Del Mastro, F. Trivaudey, V. Placet, V. Guicheret-Retel, L. Boubakar, Nonlinear Tensile Behaviour of Elementary Hemp Fibres: A Numerical Investigation of the Relationships between 3D Geometry and Tensile Behaviour, *Journal of Materials Science*, **52** (11), 2017, pp. 6591-6610, [doi:10.1007/s10853-017-0896-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-017-0896-x).
- [9] I. M. Gitman, H. Askes, and L. J. Sluys, Representative Volume: Existence and Size Determination, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **74** (16), 2007, pp. 2518–34, [doi:10.1016/j.engfracmech.2006.12.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2006.12.021).
- [10] M. Ostoja-Starzewski, “Microstructural Randomness Versus Representative Volume Element in Thermomechanics,” *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **69** (1), 2002, pp. 25–35, [doi:10.1115/1.1410366](https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1410366).
- [11] C. Geuzaine and JF Remacle, Gmsh: A Three-Dimensional Finite Element Mesh Generator with Built-in Pre-and Post-Processing Facilities, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **79** (11), 2009, pp. 1309-1331, [doi: 10.1002/nme.2579](https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.2579).
- [12] V. Placet, F. Trivaudey, O. Cisse, V. Guicheret-Retel, L. Boubakar., Diameter Dependence of the Apparent Tensile Modulus of Hemp Fibres: A Morphological, Structural or Ultrastructural Effect?, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43** (2), 2012, pp. 275–87, [doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.10.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.10.019).
- [13] O. Cisse, V. Placet, V. Guicheret-Retel, F. Trivaudey, L. Boubakar., Creep Behaviour of Single Hemp Fibres. Part I: Viscoelastic Properties and Their Scattering under Constant Climate, *Journal of Materials Science*, **50**, (4), 2015, pp. 1996–2006, [doi:10.1007/s10853-014-8767-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-014-8767-1).
- [14] V. Guicheret-Retel, O. Cisse, V. Placet, J. Beaugrand, M. Pernes, L. Boubakar, Creep Behaviour of Single Hemp Fibres. Part II: Influence of Loading Level, Moisture Content and Moisture Variation, *Journal of Materials Science*, **50** (5), 2015, pp. 2061–72, [doi:10.1007/s10853-014-8768-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-014-8768-0).
- [15] C. Poilâne, Z. Cherif, F. Richard, A. Vivet, B. Ben Doudou, J. Chen, Polymer Reinforced by Flax Fibres as a Viscoelastoplastic Material, *Composite Structures*, **112**, 2014, pp. 100–112, [doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.01.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.01.043).

ⁱ For a stationary random process, it is assumed that the statistical characteristics derived from the mean values calculated from the values at the same instant of a large number of different realizations of the process in question coincide with those which are deduced from the successive values in time of any of these realizations